

Teacher Disposition and Social Support as Influence of Student Engagement

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Abstract:- This study determined the teacher disposition, social support as predictor of student engagement in Caraga Davao Oriental. A quantitative non-experimental research utilizing the descriptive correlational research design in this study with a sample of 300 teachers. The researcher used sets of adapted survey questionnaires in obtaining data from the respondents which were subjected for content validity and reliability analysis. The data were analyzed using the Mean, Pearson- r, and Multiple Regression Analysis. The overall result revealed that the levels of teacher disposition, social support and student engagement are evident most of the time. Moreover, teacher disposition and social support has significant influence on the student engagement in Caraga Davao Oriental was proven in this study.

Keywords:- Educational Management, Teacher Disposition, Social Support, Student Engagement. Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

Student disengagement is a problem faced by many teachers. Various studies have addressed the issue of student participation in the classroom (Bennett & Boesdorfer, 2020; Sutiani, Situmorang & Silalahi, 2021). There are several reasons why this problem persists. A large part of the lack of classroom participation can be attributed to teacher attitudes and the classroom environment. The idea that student perceptions of teachers correlate with engagement is supported by her Wang (2020) who showed that classroom engagement and student success are positively correlated with classroom quality. Classroom quality was defined by teachers' emotional support, instructional support, and classroom organization. They are high school graduates who are not ready for lifelong learning (Vaughn & Winner, 2000).

Student engagement can be seen as the glue that binds all aspects of student learning and development together. Encouraging student participation has been shown to have a significant impact on students, as well as make the lessons themselves more fun, engaging and challenging. When students demonstrate high levels of behavioral, emotional, and cognitive engagement, they are likely to achieve academic excellence, be more attached to school, and have more positive social and emotional well-being. (Barkley & Major, 2020).

Given the importance of school climate, researchers read and analyzed several literature studies to identify factors that influence student participation. A teacher's temperament promotes student participation. Social support, including emotional, instrumental, evaluative, and informational support, directly contributes to student participation. Indeed, the need for professional development opportunities for administrators and teachers focused on social support is emphasized. Strong social support is also essential. This increases their self-esteem and autonomy, allowing them to deal with problems independently (Lee, 2020). On the other hand, a teacher's temperament is highly correlated with her five components of student engagement: B. Emotions - Emotional, Cognitive, and Behavioral (Bond, 2020). Furthermore, the researchers were unaware of any studies that addressed teacher disposition or social supportive behavior as an effect of student involvement in the community. With this in mind, researchers decided to conduct a study to determine whether student engagement correlated with teacher disposition and social support behavior in the community. Although there has been previous literature on associations between teacher temperament, social supportive behavior, and student engagement, these studies have focused only on bivariate relationships and have did not address the interrelationship of Few of these studies have been conducted in the field of education, especially teachers.

The study addresses three of his variables, one being the dependent variable, making this study a contribution to new knowledge. In addition, this study may raise concerns about the intended beneficiaries of this study, who may develop action plans to improve teacher disposition, social supportive behaviors, and student engagement. Yes, which justifies the need to conduct this study.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

➤ Teacher Disposition

One way for teacher educators to address this problem is to find ways to develop valid and reliable quality and assessment tools. But by its nature, the word "nature" is an ambiguous word. It is therefore not too surprising to propose that a consensus definition of properties needs to be agreed upon before discussing other aspects such as property evaluation and deployment (Valtonen, Hoang, Sointu, Näykki, Pöysä Tarhonen & Kukkonen, 2021).

Similarly, temperament has been viewed as a tendency to act on an individual's abilities (Shodipe & Ohhanu, 2021). This view suggests that the nature is active and within the capabilities of the individual. (Saultz, Lyons, Aronson, Sander, & Malin, 2021) state that Dunn (2021) defined dispositions as “attributed characteristics of a teacher that represent a trend of a teacher’s judgments and actions in ill-structured contexts (situations in which there is more than one way to solve a dilemma; even experts disagree on which way is best).

The first domain is on professional conduct. A code of ethics and professional conduct outlines the ethical principles that govern decisions and behavior at a company or organization. They give general outlines of how employees should behave, as well as specific guidance for handling issues like harassment, safety, and conflicts of interest (Lin, Chai, & Jong, 2021).

Meanwhile, teachers are duly licensed professionals who possess dignity and reputation with high moral values as well as technical and professional competence in the practice of their noble profession, they strictly adhere to, observe, and practice this set of ethical and moral principles, standards, and value (Rauscher & Badenhorst, 2021).

In the same vein, teacher dispositions are also described as “habits of mind” and “patterns of behavior,” further adding to the definition’s unwieldiness. The literature related to effective teaching and reflective practices has defined teacher dispositions as metacognitive processes that manifest as teaching. Because many of these definitions allude to a vague list of personality, behavioral, and reflective attributes, researchers continue to struggle to find an explicit and measurable definition of teaching dispositions (Hanny, Arnesen, Guo, Hansen, & Graham, 2021).

The second domain is on professional responsibility. Teachers face complex ethical dilemmas and professional tensions every day. The overarching expectation is that every teacher will apply high professional standards and sound ethical decision-making in all their work. In doing so, they will act in a way that upholds the reputation of the teaching profession, and maintains the trust and confidence of learners, their families and the public (Bukko, & Liu, 2021).

The third domain is on professional growth. Professional development domain emphasizes the ideal that teachers value having a high personal regard for the teaching profession, concern for professional development, and continuous improvement as teachers. There are strands to this domain. Strand teacher takes pride in the nobility of teachers as a profession; Strand teacher builds professional links with colleagues to enrich teaching practice; and Strand teacher reflects on the extent of the attainment of professional development goals (Carter, Onwuegbuzie, Singal, & van der Velde, 2021).

➤ *Social Support*

In many schools, teachers labor in isolation, school Effective school principals are normally the instructional leaders in their schools who guide teachers in their teaching roles. Although they are knowledgeable about what teachers do and how they can support them in their instruction, they are frequently unaware of what they need to do to support the media specialist as a collaborator with classroom teachers when they instruct students together. Unfortunately, most school principals have little or no understanding of the role of the media specialist in the instructional process. It is essential that the principal understand the role of the media specialist in the instructional process and offer support to assist in student learning (Novitasari, Asbari, Purwanto, Fahmalatif, Sudargini, Hidayati, & Wiratama, 2021).

Moreover, social support is an expansive construct that describes the physical and emotional comfort given to individuals by their family, friends, and other significant persons in their lives. Social support is purported to have a beneficial effect on health and well-being of people, and while it is a term that does not have a widely agreed upon definition in the adolescent health and development literature, it can be generally defined as the degree to which a person’s basic needs are gratified through interaction with others. The social support construct encompasses a variety of specific characteristics of an individual’s social world that might promote well-being and/or increase resistance to health problems (Cappe, Poirier, Engelberg, & Boujut, 2021).

Likewise, researchers have begun to illustrate how positive perceptions of teacher support can promote mental wellness, such that greater perceptions of teacher support are associated with higher levels of life satisfaction (Suldo et al., 2008) and subjective well-being (Suldo, Friedrich, White, Farmer, Minch et al., 2009). Moreover, supportive teacher student relationships help maintain students’ interests in academic and social pursuits, which in turn lead to better grades and more positive peer relationships (Permatasari, Ashari, & Ismail, 2021).

Notably, research has shown that the actual receipt of social support is not necessary for achieving beneficial outcomes; the mere perception that one has received support is often adequate. Such as the perception that social support is available seems to mitigate the negative impact of a stressful event and to hasten recovery even if social support is not actually verified or used. In other words, simply having the belief that one is supported, even if the adolescent does not use this support, holds positive implications for successful development (Ibrahim, Zalam, Foster, B., Afrizal, Johansyah, Saputra, & Ali, 2021).

The first domain is emotional. The more difficult to qualify parts of it is to what degree people's emotions should be included into the harm principle. It involves acting as a confidant for someone as such teacher might offer emotional support to someone by listening and offering sympathy after they've had bad news. Unfortunately this gives way pretty easily under any sort of scrutiny, not too long ago the idea of

interracial marriage offended people, and even today the idea of homosexual relations still offends many people (Aarnio, Clavert, MKangas, & Toom, 2021).

Next domain is on instrumental. Behavior is goal-directed only if: (i) it is sensitive to the contingency between action and outcome, and the outcome is desired. Based on the second condition outcome revaluation manipulations have been used to distinguish between two systems of action control. An action that is sensitive to revaluation is considered goal-directed, but if it persists despite the fact that the instrumental outcome is no longer a valued goal such as for instance, food for a satiated animal, then the action must not be goal-directed (Popa-Velea, Pristavu, Ionescu, Mihăilescu, & Diaconescu, 2021).

The third domain is appraisal. Employee engagement has emerged as a potentially important employee performance and organizational management subject. A growing body of evidence supports the relationship between the engagement of an employee at work and hotel organizational outcomes inclusive of those which are performance based. Even though the practitioners and researchers tout engagement as important work related factors, the definitions and measurements of an engagement at work, and more specifically food and beverage service engagement employees, are poorly understood (Guo, Gai, Huang, Wang, Yang, & Ling, 2021).

➤ Student Engagement

When students engage in educationally effective practices in and out of the classroom, there are a range of measurable outcomes: "The extent to which students are attracted to the activities demonstrated in university research is a measure of quality." associated with higher learning outcomes." Engagement is the quality of effort students expend in educationally meaningful activities that directly contribute to desired outcomes (Havik and Westergård, 2020).

Most teachers have seen these signs of engagement during a project, presentation, or lively classroom discussion. They wanted a glimpse into a child's inspirational inner world and to keep that wonder, excitement, and perseverance alive every day. At the same time, they may have felt handicapped by the tradition of reward and punishment. Our challenge is to overcome these very real difficulties and provide a practical model for understanding what students want and need (Ahmed, Shehata & Hassanien, 2020).

Students want and need jobs that allow them to prove and improve their self-image as competent and successful people. This is the driving force behind learning. However, in our society, success is a priority, which can be more or less the motivation. For example, highly creative people actually experience failure much more often than success (Dhall, Sharma, Goecke & Gedeon, 2020). The first area is emotional engagement. Students who are emotionally involved experience emotional responses such as interest, joy, and a sense of belonging. Some psychology studies have

explored emotional engagement related to students' academic enjoyment, including the level of interest, happiness, boredom, and anxiety students experience during schoolwork (Paulsen & McCormick, 2020).

The second domain concerns cognitive engagement. This can be understood as students' psychological importance to their own knowledge. When students are engaged cognitively, they are more focused on achieving their goals, nervous about their efforts, and comfortable with frustration. This is unique in terms of high performance. High-performing learners may be currently detached, whether they are moving to strive for themselves or are essential to achieving their goals (Bedenlier, Bond, Buntins, Zawacki-Richter, and Kerres, 2020).

The third area is behavioral engagement. Refers to student participation in classroom activities and learning. This includes adhering to rules of conduct, doing exercises when necessary, and being punctual in class. Essentially, behavioral engagement refers to educational outcomes that are critical to high school achievement and may include cooperation and communication from the facilitator. It also addresses students' investments in different aspects of school life, including: in school community and extracurricular activities (Moubayed, Injadat, Shami, Luffiyya, 2020).

➤ Correlation between Measures

Astin (1980) first developed the "participation theory". At the highest level, attempts are being made to measure the amount of physical and mental energy students expend on their academic experience.

This study is based on Martinez's paper (2001). Major and Brock (2003) argued that teachers must possess certain dispositions that integrate students' needs into the educational environment, thereby enabling learners to negotiate both cultures academically and socially. emphasized. In other words, the more strategic learners become, the more likely they are to succeed, leading to greater self-efficacy and motivation.

This research is supported by Holcombe and Wang (2010), who found that teacher social support is an indicator of student engagement with the school, represented by school engagement, school characteristics, and use of self-regulatory strategies. said to affect the development of Teacher-supported learners tend to be better at meeting their needs, resulting in less distraction and depraved behavior. Positive camaraderie is associated with greater support and involvement in school, while negative camaraderie is associated with school dropout.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

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There are three sets of questionnaires, adopted by the authors of various studies and validated by experts in questionnaire design. The adapted standardized questionnaire is content-wise, with many modifications to rank the most reliable and valid questions. Moreover, it has already been tested and proven by the author. The questionnaire was designed in a very comprehensive format with the help of validation experts so that the respondents could easily and comfortably answer each question and understand the purpose of the survey. The questionnaires used in the study were validated by experts. Overall rating was 4.00 or very good. After verification and correction, our experts approved the equipment. The questionnaire was contextually tailored to the level of the respondent.

The first part of the questionnaire addresses teacher disposition with a Cronbach alpha score of .948. This means that the items are relatively consistent and there are subscales of occupational behavior. professional responsibility. Professional Development; Addressing Diversity and Social Justice (Dottin, 2010).

Her second set of questionnaires addressing variables is social support, focusing on emotional, instrumental, evaluative and informational aspects (Littrell et al. 1994.), with a Cronbach alpha score of .921, meaning the elements are relatively consistent. The Likert scale asks individuals to check boxes/blanks in response to a number of items related to attitudes, objects, and stimuli. It is common to treat the numbers obtained from rating scales as direct measurements by calculating averages or, more generally, performing arithmetic operations.

Adapted from Lam and Jimerson (2008) to measure student participation levels. Questionnaires were used to measure the performance of students with emotional, cognitive and behavioral problems. Cronbach's alpha score is 0.911, with his 15 items on his 5-point scale from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree," indicating relatively high consistency.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, data obtained from interviewees on the impact of student engagement on teacher disposition and social support behavior is presented, analyzed and interpreted using the subproblems previously described. The flow of discussion on the mentioned subject is as follows:

The degree of temperament of the teacher. Level of social support behavior. The level of student engagement and the correlation between teacher disposition and student engagement. The relationship between social support behavior and student engagement. The extent to which a predictor variable affects student participation.

Table 1 shows the degree of teachers' attitudes towards professional behavior. professional responsibility. professional development; addressing diversity and social justice, which are the primary aims of research. As shown, the mean overall teacher temperament score is 4.21 with a calculated standard deviation of 0.38, which is quite high.

This means that the teacher's disposition is consistently practiced by interviewees. For individual items, the metric with the highest mean is Professional Behavior with a weighted average of 4.28 and a very high descriptive level. On the other hand, the highest average is a weighted average of occupational behavior of 4.27, which is quite high. On the other hand, the lowest average of teacher quality is called professional growth, with an average of 4.15 for him, and a high descriptive interpretation. A very high level of professional behavior, professional roles and behavior has always been maintained by teachers.

Teaching temperament, which was highly rated by respondents, suggests that understanding the effectiveness of a person practicing the teaching profession is largely a matter of understanding the person inside.

Table 1 Level of Teacher Disposition

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Professional Conduct	0.34	4.28	Very High
Professional Responsibility	0.29	4.27	Very High
Professional Growth	0.42	4.15	High
Commitment to Diversity and Social Justice	0.58	4.21	Very High
Overall	0.38	4.21	Very High

Dispositions from which their efforts came. This implies teachers are displaying professionalism through regular attendance and being punctual, displaying

professionalism through appropriate appearance and demeanor and demonstrating academic and professional honesty.

Various authors (Miller, 2005); Zoric, Smid et al. (2007; Sparks, 2011; Jalimao, 2019) that dispositions of teachers are unique and personal Teacher qualities, ethical awareness and high professional competence are the basis for professional integrity and essential for creating favorable conditions for play, learning and building. The right to methodological freedom and professional discretion creates a special responsibility to be open about scientific and educational decisions. Society should be confident that it is exercising professional autonomy appropriately and ethically.

Table 2 shows the extent of social supportive behavior in terms of emotional, instrumental, evaluative, and informative measures. As shown, the mean overall score for the level of social supportive behavior is 4.03 with a calculated standard deviation of 0.36, which is quite high. This means that respondents will appear frequently. The results show that she has the highest average score for 'emotional' at 4.20, which is very high. The average value of "Information" was 4.01, followed by "Evaluation" of 3.99, and "Equipment" of 3.93, all of which were highly evaluated. On the other hand, the lowest mean value for all social support behaviors is within the means range, with a mean value of 3.93.

Social support behaviors rated highly by respondents indicate that social support behaviors are often clearly perceived among teachers. Moreover, it is clear that peer support for teachers has a significant impact on their positive attitudes.

Table 2. Social Support Behavior

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Emotional	0.38	4.20	Very High
Instrumental	0.44	3.93	High
Appraisal	0.37	3.99	High
Informational	0.46	4.01	High
Overall	0.36	4.03	High

With positive social support, teachers' attitudes towards education will also improve.

This result is consistent with that of his Morberg et al. (2020) Parents agree to be involved in school decision-making when they serve on the school board or participate in organizations such as the Parent-Teacher Association. Other decision-making activities include taking leadership roles that involve sharing information with other parents.

This result is consistent with that of Chaudhry et al. (2021) found that strong relationships with teachers and school staff can dramatically increase student motivation and facilitate learning. Students who are able to develop stronger relationships are more academically engaged, have stronger social skills, and exhibit more positive behaviors. Many

authors state that parental involvement improves teacher performance because employees are happier and more outcome-oriented within the organization when they feel supported. When parents communicate better with their teachers, they are more likely to appreciate their work and assignments, and teachers feel valued by their peers.

Table 3 shows the results of the student engagement of the respondents. We calculated that the overall average score was above her 3.93. This high level can be attributed to the similarly high ratings of respondents. The reported overall average is the result of calculating the average value for that metric. From the data, we can infer that the indicators with the highest average score of 4.06 or higher are emotional, followed by the cognitive indicators with an average score of 3.90 or higher. In contrast, the lowest metric with an average score of 3.82 or higher is the behavioral metric.

The high student engagement in the Mati North district is due to the high ratings given by respondents to behavioral, cognitive and emotional indicators. Students avoid making the same mistakes themselves when checking. Students consistently performed better on assignments when they found the text particularly interesting. This shows that students need to attend school regularly to be successful. The good news about this report is that I go to school

Table 3 Level of Student Engagement

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
Affective	0.38	4.06	High
Cognitive	0.32	3.90	High
Behavioral	0.53	3.82	High
Overall	0.32	3.93	High

Lead to success in school. This may seem obvious, but underperforming schools cannot be monitored or acted upon, and failures in the public education system make it impossible for people to miss a few days of school. You might end up believing it doesn't matter that much. Consistent with the views of Hord, Huling, and Hall (2013), participation in school activities provides students with important social skills that adolescents can leverage to improve their connection with school and their academic standing. can be worn.

The results of the test to determine the association between the teacher's mood and student participation are shown in Table 4. The link was evaluated at a significance level of 0.05, as suggested by the hypothesis. The null hypothesis was rejected, as shown by an overall r-value of 0.705 and a p-value of less than 0.05. This indicates that there is a strong link between the attitude of the instructor and the level of student participation. This suggests a relationship between instructor attitude and student participation.

For professional conduct, teacher temperament correlates with student engagement measures with an r-value of 0.578, which is non-cognitively significant, and an r-value

of 0.108 with a p-value larger than 0.05, which is a significance threshold that is not significant. As a result, the significance level is significant if the teacher's dedication to

temperament is reflected in an r-value of or higher for a measure of student involvement.

Table 4. Significance of the Relationship between Social Support Behavior and Student Engagement

Teacher Disposition	Student Engagement			
	Affective	Cognitive	Behavioral	Overall
Professional Conduct	.644* (0.000)	.108 (0.063)	.519* (0.000)	.578* (0.000)
Professional Responsibility	.559* (0.000)	.141* (0.015)	.510* (0.000)	.543* (0.000)
Professional Growth	.641* (0.000)	.164* (0.004)	.541* (0.000)	.600* (0.000)
Commitment to Diversity and Social Justice	.671* (0.000)	.238* (0.000)	.655* (0.000)	.698* (0.000)
Overall	.730* (0.000)	.198* (0.001)	.649* (0.000)	.705* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level

Give social support, and within the dynamics of a healthy relationship, trust develops psychologically.

The amount of student involvement is strong, particularly when emotional is the focus. Additionally, there is a strong correlation between student participation and the teacher's attitude and social support.

The focus on professional conduct is one area where teacher dispositions are particularly strong. In terms of

emotional support, the amount of social support is strong. The amount of student involvement is strong, particularly when emotional is the focus. Student involvement and instructor attitude have a substantial link. The study's findings are consistent with Holcombe and Wang's (2019) hypothesis that learners who are encouraged by their professors would tend to fulfill their aspirations to a greater extent.

Table 5. Significance Relationship between the Social Support Behavior and Student Engagement

Social Support Behavior	Student Engagement			
	Affective	Cognitive	Behavioral	Overall
Emotional	.624* (0.000)	.225* (0.000)	.713* (0.000)	.708* (0.000)
Instrumental	.877* (0.000)	.279* (0.000)	.584* (0.000)	.754* (0.000)
Appraisal	.593* (0.000)	.567* (0.000)	.661* (0.000)	.780* (0.000)
Informational	.645* (0.000)	.382* (0.000)	.850* (0.000)	.842* (0.000)
Overall	.786* (0.000)	.410* (0.000)	.802* (0.000)	.881* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level

According to Holcombe and Wang (2019), who support this notion, instructors' social support affects the growth of an indication of students' engagement in school, as shown by their school involvement, school characteristics, and use of self-regulated strategies. Students who feel encouraged by their professors tend to fulfill their aspirations to a larger extent, which reduces distraction and bad conduct.

Furthermore, encouraging academic growth and promoting pro-social conduct in schools can both benefit from solid and accessible parental support. Teenagers can use any of these sources of assistance in this way (Habegger & Hodanbosi, 2019).

The degree to which teacher disposition and social support behavior predictor factors have on student involvement is seen in Table 6. The F-value was found to be 510.077 with

Table 6. The extent of Influence of Predictor Variables on Student Engagement

Student Engagement (Dependent Variables)				
Independent Variables	β (Standardized Coefficients)	B (Unstandardized Coefficients)	t	Sig.
Constant	.743	.109	6.824	.000
Teacher Disposition (TD)	-.011	-.010	-.243	.808
Social Support Behavior (SSB)	.890	.800	19.164	.000
R	.881			
R ²	.775			
F	510.977			
p	.000			

V. CONCLUSION

As can be gathered within the discoveries of the ponder, conclusions were drawn in this segment. The discoveries of this think about affirm the suspicions around the impact of educator mien and social bolster on the understudy engagement. Also, the consider uncovers an awfully tall level of instructor mien as seen by open instructors of Davao Oriental. The level of social bolster is tall which infers instructors endeavor to create connections with students and community whom they can depend on to supply social back, the mental state of believe develops from inside the flow of a quality relationship.

The level of understudy engagement is tall particularly in center on emotional. Besides, the educator mien and social bolster are altogether related to the understudy engagement.

The level of educator miens is exceptionally tall particularly in center on proficient conduct. The level of social bolster is tall in terms of emotional. The level of understudy engagement is tall particularly in center on full of feeling. There's a critical relationship between instructor mien and understudy engagement. The result of the ponder underpins the recommendation of Holcombe and Wang (2019) that learners' who are bolstered with their instructors will have a propensity to meet-up their wants to a more noteworthy degree, which, hence, diminishes diversion and deteriorate behavior.

RECOMMENDATION

The previous discoveries and conclusions donate way to these proposals. The instructor miens may support the exceptionally tall level. This may be done by conducting standard assessments, through numerous and progressing openings to apply their unused learning within the setting of their claim classrooms, instructors were able to decipher their unused learning into hone. The comes about of these assessments may be examined by the head of office with concerned instructors to address issues and assist make strides the usage of programs of the school to realize the organizational objectives. The tall level of social back recommended that educator teachers and instructive experts ought to consider advertising courses, proficient

advancement, or mentoring openings with experienced teachers to share the benefits of mental bolster and its consequent impacts on educator adequacy.

Moreover tthe comes about of this ponder, hence, propose that an intercession for people with a moo thankful mien to make strides their inclination to be thankful may advance their goodwill understanding of social bolster, as well as offer assistance them utilize social assets completely to fulfill their mental needs.

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